

PRODUCTION OF MCM-41 FROM RICE HUSK

K.N. Hui¹, J.Y. Lee¹, W. Guo¹, K.S. Hui^{2,*}

¹ Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Pusan National University, Pusan, Korea

² Department of Manufacturing Engineering & Engineering Management, City University of Hong Kong, Kowloon tong, Hong Kong

* Corresponding author (kwanshui@cityu.edu.hk)

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Abstract

Rice husk ash was used as the silica source to synthesize MCM-41 with microwave heating. The effect of pH on the prepared MCM-41 was investigated. X-ray diffraction (XRD) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis indicated that ordered structure MCM-41 can be synthesized in shorter time by microwave heating (1 h) compared with conventional oven heating (24 h). pH 9 was found to be the optimum condition to synthesize MCM-41 with microwave heating. The adsorption capacity of basic yellow 87 on MCM-41 prepared from rice husk was higher than that prepared by pure silicate source. The results indicated that the adsorption ability of MCM-41 prepared from rice husk could be significantly improved by controlling the preparation parameters. The low cost MCM-41 prepared from rich husk makes them potentially attractive adsorbents for the removal of dyes from aqueous solution.

1 Introduction

Every year, about 100 million tonnes of rice husk is produced globally. Directly disposing the rice husk as solid waste may result in great environmental and economic challenges. Thus, many studies have been conducted to investigate the potential use the rice husk in the past few decades. As rice husk has low moisture content (8-10 %), it is now commonly used as a biomass fuel for power generation. Rice husk has a relatively high ash ratio than other biomass and its silica content is high (92-95 %) [1]. Therefore, rice husk ash can be a potential low cost source of silica.

Rice husk ash has been used as a silica source to synthesize mesoporous silica material, such as MCM-41. It is reported that the chemical and physical properties (e.g. crystallinity and porosity) of MCM-41 obtained from rice husk ash are compatible to those obtained from typical commercial silica sources, like TEOS [2-4]. In order to utilize rice husk ash for mass production of MCM-41, a simple and fast synthesis method is

needed. However, typical MCM-41 synthesis process involves a long heating step (can up to a few days), which makes the synthesis process time and energy consuming and does not favour mass production.

In recent years, more attentions have been paid on using microwave heating on synthesis of porous materials, including MCM-41. It was found that microwave radiation can achieve fast and uniform heating, which can greatly shorten the crystallization time and more uniform crystallization can be achieved. It is reported that synthesis time of MCM-41 can be shortened to a few hours and quality of MCM-41 obtained from microwave heating is compatible to that obtained from conventional oven heating [5-7]. Although microwave heating can fasten the synthesis process, there is limited study on using rice husk ash to synthesize MCM-41 with microwave heating.

Dyes are water soluble and intensely colored substances used for the coloration of various substrates, including paper, leather, and textiles. It was estimated that about 10-15% of these dyes are released in effluents during dyeing processes. Colour removal from industry or domestic effluents has been the target of great attention in the last few years, not only because of its toxicity but mainly due to its visibility. At present, various technologies including chemical oxidation, biological treatment, coagulation–flocculation and membrane processes have been shown to be effective in reducing dye concentrations in wastewater. However these treatment processes are costly and cannot effectively be used to treat the wide range of dye wastewaters. Adsorption has been found to be superior to other techniques for pollutants removal from wastewater.

MCM-41 is mesoporous material which has high surface area, high pore volume, low mass density, continuous porosity, as well as ideally shaped pore structures [8]. MCM-41 has potential for liquid-phase separations and reactions. Moreover, MCM-41 has been reported for the adsorption and removal of inorganic [9], phenol [10], and organic vapors

[11]. Researchers pointed out that adsorption depend on the structure of dye and adsorbent [12]. However, the current research is limited to a few kinds of dyes including reactive brilliant red X-3B, basic violet 10 and methylene blue [13-14]. Moreover, basic yellow 87 is a one of most common pollutant contained in hair dyeing wastewater. To our knowledge, there is no research on addressing the removal of basic yellow 87 from aqueous solution by MCM-41.

In this study, MCM-41 synthesis with conventional oven heating and microwave heating were compared. The effect of pH on MCM-41 synthesis with microwave heating was investigated. Batch method was employed to study the adsorption of basic yellow 87 in water on different MCM-41 samples.

2 Experiments

2.1 Chemicals

Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) powder, in analytical reagent grade, was purchased from JHD, PR China. Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) pellet and concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCl), all in ACS reagent grade, were purchased from Riedel de Haen, Germany.

2.2 Preparation of Rice Husk Ash

The rice husk ash was prepared based on the method described in literature with some modifications [15]. Rice husk was first acid leached with 3.0 M HCl solution at 100°C. The acid leached rice husk was then washed with water to remove the excess acid on the surface and dried in oven overnight at 100°C. The dried rice husk was then calcined at 600°C for 6 hr to obtain rice husk ash. The ash obtained was white in colour.

2.3 Synthesis of MCM-41

MCM-41 with rice husk ash as the silica source was prepared based on the method described in literature with some modifications [3]. Rice husk ash was first mixed with 3.75 M NaOH solution and stirred overnight to extract the silicate from the ash. CTAB was dissolved in water to obtain a clear solution. The two solutions were then mixed stirred for 1 hr. The mixture had the molar composition of 1.0 SiO₂ : 3.0 NaOH : 0.25 CTAB : 180 H₂O. The pH value of the mixture was adjusted to a desired value by adding 3.0 M HCl solution. The mixture was then heated in microwave oven at 100°C for 1 hr for crystallization. After the heating process, the solid was recovered by centrifuge. The solid was dried in

oven overnight at 100°C and calcined at 550°C for 6 hr. The sample was named as MW-MCM-41. For conventional oven heating, the mixture was heated in oven at 100°C for 24 hr for crystallization. After the heating process, the solid was recovered by centrifuge. The solid was dried in oven overnight at 100°C and calcined at 550°C for 6 hr. The sample was named as HT-MCM-41

2.4 Characterization

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of samples were recorded on a Siemens D500 powder X-ray diffractor with Cu K α radiation (= 0.15418 nm). The measurement condition of XRD are 40 kV and 30 mA, with scanning speed of 1°/min. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) morphologies of samples were observed on a Philips CM-20 Transmission electron microscope with an acceleration voltage of 0.5 - 30.0 kV.

2.5 Dye Removal Study

The basic dye, Basic yellow 87, was purchased from Artenano Co., Ltd. of Hong Kong, and it was used as received without further purification. The dye adsorbate was first dried at 105 °C for 24 h to remove moisture before use. The molecular structure and UV-visible spectra of Basic yellow 87 are shown in Fig. 1.

The dye adsorption data from water solutions were obtained by the immersion method. Adsorption experiments were carried out by agitating (at 150 rpm) 0.05 g adsorbent in 50 mL basic dye 87 solution of 400 mg/l initial concentration at 30 °C for 24 h. The solution and solid phase were separated by centrifugation at 2000 rpm for 5 min in a Hettich EBA 21 centrifuge. All basic yellow 87 solutions were diluted with distilled water and analysed by PerkinElmer Lambda 35 UV-VIS Spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 411 nm. The dye adsorption capacity at equilibrium, Q_e (mg/g), can be calculated from

$$Q_e = \frac{V(C_0 - C_e)}{1000m} \quad (1)$$

where C_0 (mg/l) is the initial dye concentration in liquid phase, C_e (mg/l) is the dye concentration in liquid phase at equilibrium, V (l) is the total volume of dye solution and m (g) is the mass of adsorbent.

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 XRD analysis

The XRD patterns of MCM-41 synthesized by microwave heating (MW-MCM-41) and oven

heating (HT-MCM-41) are shown in Fig. 2. Peaks are observed at 2.4° and 4.0° for MW-MCM-41 and only at 2.4° for HT-MCM-41. According to literature, XRD pattern of highly crystallinity MCM-41 should have peaks at 2θ of 2.4°, 4.0°, 4.4° and 6.0° [16]. For MW-MCM-41, main peaks at 2.4° and 4.0° are observed but peak at 4.4° and 6.0° are absent. This indicated MW-MCM-41 is MCM-41 material but is not well crystalline. For HT-MCM-41, its peak intensity at 2.4° is weak, indicating it is not in ordered hexagonal structure. The results showed that MCM-41 material could be synthesized by using rice husk ash as the silica source with microwave heating method at 100°C with very short reaction time. However, higher temperature may be needed to obtain a more crystalline product [17].

3.2 Effect of pH

The effect of pH on MCM-41 synthesis was also investigated. Fig. 3 shows XRD patterns of MCM-41 synthesized at pH 8 to 12 with microwave heating. The intensity of peak at 2.4° and 4.0° increases as the pH drops and reaches the maximum at pH 9. A possible explanation is at high pH, the solubility of silicates is high, which is difficult to form particles or chains [18-19]. The interaction between cetyltrimethylammonium ions and silicate may be affected by the high OH⁻ concentration. Therefore, the MCM-41 synthesized at high pH is poorly polymerized and the hexagonal structure of MCM-41 is not stable, which collapses easily upon drying or calcination. However, for pH lower than 9, the polycondensation of the silicates may be too rapid that the silicates aggregate easily [18-19]. Therefore, the sample obtained at pH 8 had a poor the hexagonal structure. Fig. 4 shows the TEM morphology of MW-MCM-41 synthesized at pH 9. The hexagonal array of MCM-41 can be found on MW-MCM-41. The pore diameter is around 2 - 3 nm.

3.3 Dye Removal

The adsorption capacity of different MCM-41 samples was reported in Table 1. The MCM-41 samples were found to be effective as adsorbent for basic yellow 87 from aqueous solutions. Moreover, the adsorption capacity of MCM-41 was found to be dependent on the synthesis pH. In the range of pH 8 to 10, with the pH value increasing, the adsorption capacity of MCM-41 increased firstly and then decreased, and at pH 9 the adsorption capacity of MCM-41 reached the maximum. The adsorption capacity of MCM-41 prepared from rice husk was

higher than that prepared by pure silicate source. The results indicated that the adsorption ability of MCM-41 prepared from rice husk could be significantly improved by controlling the preparation parameters. The low cost MCM-41 prepared from rich husk makes them potentially attractive adsorbents for the removal of dyes from aqueous solution.

4 Conclusions

MCM-41 materials have been synthesized by microwave heating with rice husk ash as the silica source. Shorter synthesized time has been achieved by microwave heating as compare with conventional oven heating. pH 9 was found to be the optimum pH for MCM-41 synthesis. The results indicated that the adsorption ability of MCM-41 prepared from rice husk could be significantly improved by controlling the preparation parameters. The low cost MCM-41 prepared from rich husk makes them potentially attractive adsorbents for the removal of dyes from aqueous solution.

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Fig. 1 (a) Molecular formula and (b) UV-visible spectra of Basic yellow 87 (chemical formula: $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{S}$; Molecular weight: 337.4 g/mol)

Fig. 2. XRD patterns of MCM-41 synthesized at pH 10 with oven heating and microwave heating.

Fig. 3. XRD patterns of MCM-41 synthesized with microwave heating at pH 8 to 12.

Fig.4. TEM image of MW-MCM-41 synthesized with microwave heating method at pH 9.

Table 1. The adsorption capacity of basic yellow 87 on different MCM41 samples

Sample no.	Sample name	Adsorption capacity (mg/g)
1	MCM41-pH8-MW (from Rice husk)	23.66
2	MCM41-pH9-MW (from Rice husk)	42.73
3	MCM41-pH10-MW (from Rice husk)	33.34
4	MCM41-pH10-MW (from Na Silicate)	23.19